

METHODS FOR DETERMINING STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE ON THE SUBJECT OF ENGINEERING GRAPHICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14011906>

Abstract. *This article vividly highlights the qualimetric system for evaluating students' acquired knowledge and the effectiveness of the teaching methodology of the subject. The expediency of constantly updating teaching methods, and sometimes the use of game technologies in teaching, is emphasized in order to achieve a high level of skill of students in teaching "Descriptive geometry and engineering graphics".*

Keywords: *teaching methodology, individual survey, graphic work, geometric surfaces, frontal survey, spatial thinking, projection.*

An important and necessary part of the educational process is to take into account the academic performance of students, on the correct formulation of which the success of learning depends. Mastering the methodology of testing knowledge in engineering graphics and grading should be considered one of the difficult tasks facing a young teacher. Checking and evaluating students' knowledge perform the following functions: controlling, teaching, educating, developing. The controlling function is the main one, and the teaching, educating and developing functions are concomitant, although very important.

The listed functions define the main pedagogical requirements for the organization of verification and assessment of knowledge: systematic and regular monitoring.

Control over both the depth and strength of knowledge acquisition and the timely formation of certain skills and abilities; objectivity of control and assessments; making assessments in accordance with the requirements of the program for the level of knowledge, skills and abilities;

The objectivity of control (is determined by its organization, in which, in a minimum time, with the help of a sufficient number of test tasks and questions, it is possible to identify knowledge from a large number of students)[2]

In the process of teaching engineering graphics to students, the current and final forms of knowledge testing are widely used, for which oral and written surveys, independent graphic works are used.

Oral questioning is the most widespread in practice. However, it should be noted that it is the most difficult type of knowledge verification, as it depends on how students have prepared their independent assignments.

The methods of oral questioning are individual, frontal and compacted questioning.

An individual survey is not widely used in teaching engineering graphics due to the specifics of the subject. In an individual survey, the student is called to the blackboard for a detailed answer to the assessment. At the same time, students do not retell the text of the textbook, but, based on previously studied material, independently explains the material.

An example of an individual survey is reading assembly drawings from training tables. When planning an individual survey in class, the teacher must solve a number of questions for himself. For example: who should I call for questioning? How many students will be interviewed individually? What will the rest of the students be doing at this time? How long will the students' answers take?

Questions about what to check and how to ask are also difficult for a young specialist. Modern didactics and methodology suggest asking students questions that would allow them to identify an understanding of cause-and-effect relationships, the ability to analyze, compare, etc.

Having called a student for an individual survey, the teacher most often suggests that the rest of the students carefully listen to a friend's answer, supplement it and correct mistakes. When the teacher needs to listen to the answer of a low-achieving student, it is recommended that at this time the rest of the students be offered to do some independent work.

The method of conducting general answers to questions is common in teaching engineering graphics. Conducting a general survey requires a large number of students to search for answers at the same time. The front-end survey with the answer itself embodies the functions of control and training, without spending too much time. It should not be forgotten that the front-end survey also has its drawbacks from the point of view that this cannot form a complete picture of the knowledge gained on the basis of the mentioned topic.[1] In the case of a mixed answer to the same question, several answers to the same question may be offered. With an oral response, one of them can complete several tasks. This method is much more difficult for the teacher, since students are mostly busy doing the given graphic work.

This method is most often used in assessing students' knowledge. The disadvantage of this method is that in this case, the task of teaching the student becomes sluggish, since students are mainly engaged in performing this graphic work. This method is considered much more useful for checking how well it was understood by students after completing one section and giving a final grade. A drawing is a test of practical work performed independently of the methods of in-depth verification in geometry and engineering graphics. In the examination of independent graphic work, the control function is aimed at an educational and upbringing goal, but the tasks should be evaluated rationally, determining whether the student did it himself or not.

The independent work given during the lesson should be checked by the teacher for what purpose, for example, was the task completed by the student 100%? When you get acquainted with the question "How to do it?", everyone will quickly get acquainted with the student's independent work. If a new topic depends on this independent work, it should be discussed in front of everyone, explaining the task. If the assignment is given on topics well mastered by students, then it will be limited to checking the notebook. The method of checking basic knowledge is to verify that students have completed the graphic work. [1] In the program "Drawing in geometry", graphic work will be planned, which the student must master.

Extremely easy tasks do not enrich the student's knowledge. And extremely difficult tasks deprive students of self-confidence, create a nervous state. When planning a lesson during which a graphic task is performed, help should be provided to a student who is unable to master the topic well. It is necessary to examine yourself and hang up the plan of the graphic work to be done so that it is visible in the study room. The test is one of the main graphic works. The supervisor needs to explain the procedure for performing graphic work before receiving the test, clarify the questions asked by the students. For students who do graphic work quickly, a separate assignment

should also be prepared. The function of the control work is to determine to what extent the specified topic has been mastered. Working on the errors of the completed graphic work performs a training function. During the review of the control case, the supervisor must indicate on the board which shortcomings are common and which are eliminated individually.

When teaching drawing in geometry and engineering graphics, the performance of individual independent graphic tasks is widely used.

This type of ongoing tasks performs both control and training tasks. Independent work is carried out as if it were part of the training. Independent work helps to determine the level of assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities by students on a separate topic or section. Control and independent work are carried out when there is confidence that students have mastered most of the topic they have covered. To ensure the quality of the verification of graphic work, it is necessary to plan it, focusing on the standards of the ESCD:

1. The drawing is executed according to all the rules (the frame line is drawn, the corner stamp, the dimensions are correctly indicated)

2. Checking the correctness of the drawing (attach importance to the connection of projections, correctly executed line types, depending on the task, and the correctness of the answer).

Highlight the typical mistakes made by students after the test and teach them how to eliminate them. To show the weak side of students by the teacher, it is necessary to compile a report table to determine the graphical readiness of the group, comparisons in various forms of errors found in graphic works. Let's take an example of table shapes in an approximate version. Accounting for errors should be carried out in such a way that the mistakes of each student are taken into account:

1. According to the results of the oral survey, the grade "excellent" "5" is given to the following students:

a) he has mastered the mentioned program well, depending on the given topic, can tell the material he has passed in his own words, is well versed in conventional signs and drawing rules,

b) can give a clear answer to the question, understands the educational material well, has sufficient knowledge ;

C) does not make mistakes, but makes some minor mistakes when reading the drawing. the rating "good" " 4 " is given according to the following points;

a) has mastered the curriculum well, but the lack of spatial imagination is the reason for the shortcomings that are inherent in reading the drawing, knows the rules of the drawing and the signs;

b) answers correctly, the conditional value is in a logical sequence;

c) makes some mistakes when reading the drawing, waiting for the teacher to correct it.

A satisfactory grade of " 3" is given according to the following points:

a) does not have a solid basic program, but has mastered most of the rules of drawing and conventional signs;

b) cannot fully answer the question posed, there is no sequence of answers;

c) reads the drawing uncertainly, constantly needs the help of a teacher.

An unsatisfactory grade of " 2 " is given in the following :

a) does not understand most of the educational material;

b) the sequence of answers is built incorrectly, the level of errors cannot be corrected even by the teacher.

The score " 1 " is given in the following points;

a) does not understand the training program at all, does not have any knowledge.

When evaluating graphic practical work, an excellent grade of "5" is given to the following students:

a) draws confidently, the notebook is ordered, the graphic work is done correctly;

b) can easily use the reference book;

c) does not allow errors in the drawing, but allows imperfections that do not matter.

The score " 4 " is given in the following points;

a) independently, but without much difficulty, executes and reads the drawing, maintaining relative order;

b) uses a reference book, but in the main inscription makes a mistake;

c) makes mistakes that do not matter much in the speech, corrects them independently on the oral instructions of the teacher.

A satisfactory grade of " 3" is given according to the following points:

a) does not have a solid basic program, but has mastered most of the rules of drawing and conventional signs;

b) cannot fully answer the question posed, there is no sequence of answers;

c) reads the drawing uncertainly, constantly needs the help of a teacher.

The score " 2 " is given in the following cases;

a) does not perform graphic work, does not hold in his hands a drawing that must be completed independently;

b) performs the drawing with the help of a teacher, makes an error in the sequence.

The score " 1 " is given in the following cases;

if the student has not prepared a graphic work, he does not have knowledge and skills in the educational program at all.

When making an annual assessment, it is necessary to rely on the supervisor's order to conduct independent graphic and practical work of students during the year.

The arithmetic mean should not be included in the score. Perhaps the student has understood less about the graphic works that he performed earlier, by the end of the year his knowledge may increase. The projective knowledge and spatial imagination of more students will become the basis for mastering science.

This should be taken into account when conducting an overall assessment. When evaluating students, it should be remembered that the assessment characterizes only the knowledge of students. It should not be a reward or a means of punishment.[3] It is important to observe strict objectivity when grading, since a strong student may not be ready for the lesson, and a low-achieving student may learn the lesson material well.

In order to maintain objectivity when making annual grades, it is necessary to rely on teacher's observations about students and on data from the analysis of graphic and independent works.

The estimate cannot be output as some kind of arithmetic mean. Grades are the basis for studying the entire course of engineering graphics.

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